

SYNTHESIS AND STUDY OF PROPERTIES OF DERIVATIVES OF NATURAL AND SYNTHETIC PETROLEUM ACIDS

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Abstract

Among the derivatives of natural and synthetic petroleum acids, esters are one of those that have the greatest practical importance. In this article, ketoesters of natural and synthetic petroleum acids were obtained and their properties were studied. The structure of the obtained ketoesters was confirmed with the help of IR – spectral analysis. Due to the low freezing point of ketoesters obtained on the basis of vinyl ketones of natural and synthetic petroleum acids, they were used as a depressant additive in diesel fuels. It was found that when adding 0.2% esters of methoxyethyl ketone and isopropoxyethyl ketone to diesel fuel, the freezing temperature of diesel fuel drops by 30 units. In accordance with OZ DST – 989 2001 standards, the physical and chemical properties of diesel fuel added with depressor additives (ketoesters) were studied and it was determined that the requirements of the standard were fully met.

Keywords: natural and synthetic petroleum acids, depressor additive, diesel fuel, freezing temperature, ketoesters, methoxyethyl ketone, isopropoxyethyl ketone.

Introduction

Organic acids and their derivatives are increasingly used in the national economy. Petroleum is one of the sources of organic acids. The amount of petroleum acids in oils ranges from 0.07-2.4%, and in Azerbaijani oils from 0.1-1.6%. Petroleum acids are a product of alkaline processing of petroleum distillates and serve as a cheap source of raw materials for obtaining a number of industrial products - solvents, aniline dyes and vulcanized rubber, varnish and paint components, plasticizers for synthetic resins, lubricants, surfactants. Practically, petroleum acids are quite valuable. Products made from these acids are considered useful and their formulation is extremely complex. As plasticizers, surfactants, fuel and oil additives, and inhibitors of steel corrosion, natural petroleum acids are significant raw materials in the petrochemical industry. Despite the fact that natural petroleum acids and their derivatives have various uses, they are among the limited products of the petrochemical industry due to the small amount of these acids in oil. The solution to this limitation is the conversion of naphthenic hydrocarbons into acids, i.e. the synthetic production of petroleum acids [1, 2, 3, 4].

Petroleum acids have a potential amount in the oxygenated compounds of oil, and are of actual importance because they allow obtaining various valuable industrial products by separating from petroleum. Substances obtained as a result of synthesis reactions based

on petroleum acids are of wide interest and are considered relevant as they have wide and multi-field applications. The presence of halogen atoms, epoxide group, double and triple bonds in the esters molecule makes it possible to use them successfully, especially in oxidation, hydroxide, dimerization, aminomethylation, and in hydration with the formation of new derivatives of petroleum acids. In all cases, the properties of the final products mostly depend on the structure and nature of the petroleum acids. Adding petroleum acids and their derivatives to diesel fuel is a trend that shows promise for the usage of these materials. Diesel fuel may be upgraded to high-quality fuel that satisfies contemporary environmental standards by adding esters derived from petroleum acids and diatomic alcohols [5, 6, 7].

The presented article discusses the synthesis of ketoester derivatives of natural and synthetic petroleum acids and their use as a depressant additive in diesel fuels.

Experimental part

Esterification reaction between propargyl, propargyloxyethyl alcohols and natural and synthetic petroleum acids in the presence of an ionic liquid catalyst – piperidine hydrosulfate $[C_5H_{10}HN^+H]HSO_4^-$ is carried out successfully in benzene at a temperature of 80-85°C, and esters are obtained with a yield of 80-90%. The reaction mechanism can be shown as follows:

The acylation reactions of natural and synthetic petroleum acids with the above-mentioned unsaturated alcohols were carried out by the following methodology:

Taking the reaction components – mol ratio of natural and synthetic petroleum acids to acetylene alcohols as 1: (1,2 - 1,4), 40 ml of benzene solvent was added to the three-throat flask with dropping funnel, thermometer, reverse cooler and mixer. When the temperature

reaches 90°C, chloral anhydride of petroleum acids is started to be supplied from the dropping.

The start of the reaction is determined by the separation of hydrogen chloride. In order to capture hydrogen chloride, hydrogen chloride is combined with an Erlenmeyer flask through a glass tube where an aqueous solution of 150 ml of 0.01N sodium hydroxide is added. It is determined by periodically titrating the

amount of hydrogen chloride released. After the separation of HCl stopped, the mixing of the reaction mixture at a temperature of 85-100°C was continued again for 20 minutes. After the end of the reaction, they wash off the reaction mass first with weak sodium carbonate,

and then with distilled water. Then they dry on calcium chloride. After expelling the solvent (benzene) under atmospheric pressure and expelling the remaining ester mass under vacuum, their physico-chemical properties were studied and presented in Table 1.

Table 1.

Physico-chemical properties of acetylene esters

Acetylene esters of natural and synthetic petroleum acids	Boiling temperature, °C	n_D^{20}	ρ_4^{20} , kg/m ³	Acid number, KOH/g	Freezing temperature, °C	Yield, % (wt.)
RCOOCH ₂ C≡CH						
NPA	116-179	1,4589	972,7	0,16	- 63	84,4
SPA	113-172	1,4490	968,9	0,19	- 64	83,6
RCOOCH ₂ CH ₂ OCH ₂ C≡CH						
NPA	159-244	1,4711	981,6	0,3	-58	82,4
SPA	157-241	1,4715	983,5	0,6	-60	86,3

Continuing the study of the properties of acetylene esters, we subjected them to a hydration reaction in order to obtain their ketoesters.

Here, $n = 0, 1$. The reaction takes place with the presence of a catalyst ($\text{HgSO}_4/\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4$) at a temperature of 75°C, and the yield of esters is 80-90%. The structure of received ketoesters was confirmed with the help of

IR spectra. The absorption band at 1710 cm⁻¹ indicates the carbonyl group ($\text{CH}_3-\text{C}=\text{O}$) and there are no signals for the characteristic ($-\text{C}\equiv\text{CH}$) proton groups.

The physicochemical properties of ketoesters obtained on the basis of acetylene esters of natural and synthetic petroleum acids were studied and presented in Table 2. Their properties show that they can be used as modifiers for polymeric materials and as building monomers in unsaturated polyesters.

Table 2.

Physico-chemical properties of ketoesters obtained from the hydrolysis of acetylene esters of natural and synthetic petroleum acids

Structural formula of ketoesters	T_b , °C 0,4-0,5 kPa	Yield, % (wt.)	n_D^{20}	ρ_4^{20} , kg/m ³	T_f , °C	$V_{100^\circ\text{C}}$, mm ² /sec
RCOOCH ₂ COCH ₃						
NPA	121-144	85,9	1,4893	851,9	-41	2,3
SPA	122-146	83,8	1,4889	852,7	-43	2,4
RCOOCH ₂ CH ₂ OCH ₂ COCH ₃						
NPA	140-160	80,3	1,4904	886,5	-34	3,24
SPA	130-150	81,4	1,4906	888,3	-33	3,45

Hydration of vinyl ketones of natural and synthetic petroleum acids in an acidic medium at a temperature of 80°C produces β -oxyethyl keto alcohol with a yield of 66-69% (wt.). Mercury sulfate acidified with sulfuric acid was used as a reaction catalyst.

Obtaining keto alcohols is done as follows:

1 g of HgSO_4 and 20 ml of H_2O acidified with H_2SO_4 are placed in a reaction flask equipped with a thermometer and a mechanical stirrer. Then 0.1 ml of vinyl ketone is added to the mixture with stirring. The resulting mixture is heated at 80°C for 2 hours. The next day, the obtained mixture is washed with water, the aqueous layer is extracted with ester, dried with CaCl_2 , and after expelling the ester, the residue is expelled under vacuum.

The physico-chemical properties of the obtained product are as follows:

Boiling temperature – 138-147 °C/0.4 kPa; n_{20}^D – 1.4688; ρ_4^{20} – 897.8 kg/m³; yield – 66.8 % (wt.).

When compared with the original vinyl ketone, the IR spectra of the products do not include the characteristic absorption bands (985-990 and 1625-1645 cm⁻¹) characteristic of vinyl groups, but the absorption bands of 3445-3455 cm⁻¹ characteristic of the hydroxyl group are present.

Synthesized ketoalcohols to get ketoglycidyl esters, suitable glycidyl esters were obtained by dehydrochlorination of chlorohydrin formed by the interaction of epichlorohydrin in the presence of boron trifluoride with the addition of KOH. The yield of glycidyl esters was between 68-71%.

The reaction proceeds as follows:

The synthesis of glycidyl esters of ketoalcohols was carried out as follows:

After adding 0.3 mol keto alcohol and 0.1 ml $\text{BF}_3\text{O}(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)_2$, it is cooled to $0-5^\circ\text{C}$ and mixed with 15.5g of epichlorohydrin. The reaction mass is stirred at a temperature of $20-25^\circ\text{C}$ for 4 hours. After expelling the unreacted components, the residue is dissolved in 0.1 liter of ester, 10 g of KOH tablets are added with stirring and cooling ($10-15^\circ\text{C}$). The reaction mixture is again stirred at 20°C for 3 hours. After removing the solvent, we obtained the glycidyl esters by evaporating under vacuum. Physico-chemical properties of obtained esters were as follows:

Boiling temperature – $168-179^\circ\text{C}/0,4\text{ kPa}$; $n_{20}^D - 1.4716$; $\rho_4^{20} - 912,5\text{ kg/m}^3$; yield – $69,3\%$ (wt.).

where R is a naphthenic radical and $\text{R}^1 = -\text{CH}_3, -\text{C}_2\text{H}_5, -\text{C}_3\text{H}_7, -\text{C}_4\text{H}_9$.

So, the following ketoesters of natural and synthetic petroleum acids were synthesized.

1. $\text{R}^1 = -\text{CH}_3$ (RCOCH₂CH₂OCH₃ – Methoxyethylketone ester of natural and synthetic petroleum acids);
2. $\text{R}^1 = -\text{C}_2\text{H}_5$ (RCOCH₂CH₂OC₂H₅ – Ethoxyethylketone ester of natural and synthetic petroleum acids);

IR-spectra of glycidyl esters do not have $3435-3440\text{ cm}^{-1}$ characteristic of the hydroxyl group of the first taken ketoalcohols, a band is observed at $3070-3080\text{ cm}^{-1}$ characteristic of epoxide groups.

It is known that groups with electron acceptors activated by the action of alkaline agents enter into a condensation reaction with vinyl ketones with double bond and an engine hydrogen atom. Therefore, when naphthyl β - alkoxides are obtained under the influence of sodium salts of suitable alcohols, both naphthyl β -chloroethyl ketones and naphthyl vinyl ketones react according to the following scheme.

3. $\text{R}^1 = -\text{C}_3\text{H}_7$ (RCOCH₂CH₂OC₃H₇ – Isopropoxyethylketone ester of natural and synthetic petroleum acids);

4. $\text{R}^1 = -\text{C}_4\text{H}_9$ (RCOCH₂CH₂OC₄H₉ – Butoxyethylketone ester of natural and synthetic petroleum acids).

Physicochemical properties of synthesized ketoesters of natural and synthetic petroleum acids are given in Table 3.

Table 3.

Physicochemical properties of ketoesters of natural and synthetic petroleum acids

Ketoesters of natural and synthetic petroleum acids	Reaction conditions		Boiling limit, $^\circ\text{C}$ (1,3kPa)	Yield, % (wt.)	Physical and chemical properties		
	RCOCl: :R'OH	T, $^\circ\text{C}$			ρ_4^{20} g/cm ³	n_D^{20}	T _f , $^\circ\text{C}$
Methoxyethylketone NPA	1:1,2	30	119-143	82,7	0,9202	1,4737	-54
SPA	1:1,2	30	114-138	83,6	0,9204	1,4758	-57
Ethoxyethylketone NPA	1:1,2	30	127-145	81,3	0,9421	1,4778	-52
SPA	1:1,2	30	121-139	82,4	0,9423	1,4781	-55
Isopropoxyethylketone NPA	1:1,3	35	134-157	79,1	0,9533	1,4787	-56
SPA	1:1,3	35	129-152	80,2	0,9536	1,4789	-54
Butoxyethylketone NPA	1:1,3	40	139-164	72,8	0,9684	1,4811	-57
SPA	1:1,3	40	132-157	73,1	0,9687	1,4818	-58

The structure of the obtained esters was studied with the help of infrared rays and nuclear magnetic resonance.

The low freezing temperature properties of these ketoesters of natural and synthetic petroleum acids

have been suggested how they affect the freezing temperature by applying them as depressor additives in diesel fuels. We evaluated the activity of depressor additives according to GOST 20287-74 standard.

Table 4.

Effect of ketoesters (additives) added to diesel fuel on the freezing temperature of diesel fuel

Ketoesters of natural petroleum acid	Mass of depressor additive, %	Freezing temperature of diesel fuel, °C
Methoxyethylketone	0,1	-36
	0,2	-40
Isopropoxyethylketone	0,1	-40
	0,2	-40

The effect of synthesized esters on the freezing temperature of diesel fuel was tested at H. Aliyev Oil Refinery. The freezing temperature of diesel fuel itself was -10°C . The data in Table 3 show that not all synthesized esters have the same effect on the freezing point of diesel fuel. For example, when adding 0.2% methoxyethyl ketone and isopropoxyethyl ketone, the freezing temperature of diesel fuel drops by 30 units.

The physico-chemical parameters of diesel fuel with the optimal amount of depressor additive – ketoesters of petroleum acids added according to the OZ DST 989-2001 standard are given in Table 5 and it was found that the physico-chemical indicators of the studied diesel fuel fully meet the requirements of the standard, including low temperature properties.

Table 5.

Properties of diesel fuel with depressor additive according to OZ DST 989-2001 standard

Indicators	OZ DST 989-2001 standard	Diesel fuel	
		Without additive	With additive
Density at 20°C , at most	860	835	837
Cetane number, at least	45	50	50
Fractional composition, $^{\circ}\text{C}$:			
50%, at most	280	264	266
96% at most	350	342	343
Kinematic viscosity 20°C , mm^2/s	3,0 - 6,0	3,0	3,01
Freezing temperature $^{\circ}\text{C}$, the highest	-10	-14	-40
Boiling point, the highest	-6	-8	-16
Ignition temperature, lowest:			
For locomotives, marine diesels and gas turbines	62	-	57
For general purpose diesels	40	55	57
Sulfur content, % (wt.) when it burns, the most			
Mercaptan sulfur, the most	0,01	0,0003	0,0003
Water-soluble acids and alkalis		-	
Acidity $\text{mg KOH}/100 \text{ cm}^3$, highest in fuel	6	-	
Ash content, % most	0,01	0,003	0,003
Filtering coefficient	3	2	2

Conclusions

Ketoesters were obtained on the basis of acetylene esters of natural and synthetic petroleum acids in the presence of the $\text{HgSO}_4/\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4$ catalyst and their physico-chemical properties were studied. It was determined that they can be applied as modifiers for polymeric materials, as well as a building monomer in the composition of unsaturated polyesters. Then ketoesters were synthesized on the basis of vinyl ketones of natural and synthetic petroleum acids, and due to the property of low freezing temperatures of these ketoesters, they were used as a depressant additive in diesel fuels. It was determined that when adding 0.2% methoxyethyl ketone and isopropoxyethyl ketone, the freezing temperature of diesel fuel drops by 30 units. Properties of diesel fuel with depressor additive (ketoesters) according to OZ DST 989-2001 standard it was found that diesel fuel fully meet the requirements of the standard, including low temperature properties. So, the conducted research - the synthesis of petroleum acid esters and their testing in diesel fuel as depressor additives shows

that the low temperature properties of diesel fuels can be adjusted. It is possible to use diesel fuels with a freezing temperature of -40°C in the northern regions of Azerbaijan.

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